

**EFFECT OF IRRIGATION REGIMES ON GREEN MASS
PRODUCTIVITY OF MAIZE VARIETIES**

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Abstract. This article presents the results of research on the effect of irrigation methods on the yield of green mass of maize varieties "Uzbekistan-601 ESV", "Karasuv-350 AMV" and "Uzbekistan-300 MV" grown as main and repeated crops in the conditions of moderately saline, meadow-alluvial soils of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. According to the results of the research, in the conditions of moderately saline, meadow-alluvial soils of the southern Aral Sea region of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the variety of maize "Uzbekistan-300 MV" was grown with a soil moisture of 70-70-60% before irrigation, in the main crop in the 1-2-0 irrigation system, repeated crop as 0-1-0 system irrigation was found to be acceptable. Then, the highest green mass was 93,9 c/ha in the average 3 years (after grain harvesting) when grown as a main crop, and 36,0 c/ha in repeated crop.

Keywords: meadow-alluvial soils, irrigation methods, maize varieties, main crop, repeated crop, green mass, productivity.

Introduction. Farming in the soil-climate conditions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan differs sharply in a number of complexities compared to other regions of our country. The climate is relatively dry, the soil is in a poor state of reclamation, and it is saline to varying degrees. In this situation, secondary

salinization can be observed if irrigation is not carried out properly. Therefore, development of optimal irrigation methods in the maintenance of agricultural crops, including maize varieties, in order to obtain a high yield from them, is an important task.

It is known that, along with maize grain yield, its green mass is an important source of feed in animal husbandry. Grain and green mass of maize varies depending on soil and climate conditions, varieties, agrotechnics of cultivation.

By M.R. Amin Yahya [1; 28-31-p.] mentioned that on the mountainous red-brown soils of North Yemen 45,7-55,75 c/ha of mid-season Txama hybrid maize green mass without exceeding the permissible limits for irrigation with conditionally treated municipal wastewater, contamination of soil and plant products, the use of underground water for irrigation causes a decrease in the yield of green mass of maize by 8-11% and 17-27%, respectively, in comparison with irrigation with wastewater, it is necessary to strictly maintain the optimal water regime of the soil in the technology of maize irrigation.

In the experiments of S.S. Ishmetov., F.R. Abdiev [2; 214-217-p], the following information was obtained as a result of scientific research, such as determining the yield of green mass of maize variety samples and determining grain yield. In parallel with the grain yield, the yield of green mass was found to be 33.8 c/ha in the Liniya 35 sample, and 60,5 c/ha in the local Kelajak 100 sample.

The study investigated the effect of irrigation procedures on the yield of green mass of maize varieties.

Research methods. The researches were conducted in the experimental farm of Karakalpakstan Agricultural Scientific Research Institute in 2020-2022 as the main and repeated crops of "Uzbekistan-601 ESV", "Karasuv-350 AMV" and "Uzbekistan-300 MV" maize varieties. Each variety was irrigated with 60-60-60, 70-70-60 and 80-80-60% soil moisture compared to limited field moisture capacity before irrigation, and green mass yield was studied after grain harvest.

The experiment was carried out in 9 variants in the main and repeated crops.

The area of each plot is 480 m² (row length 50 m, width 8 rows 0,6x8=480 m²), of which 240 m² is taken into account. The experiment was in 3 replications, and all variants were systematically placed in the same tier.

The soil of the experimental field is a semi-hydromorphic soil, the level of underground water is 2-3 m.

Analysis and results. In the experiment, research on the effect of irrigation procedures on the accumulation of green mass (leaf stem) of maize varieties was studied in the main and repeated periods of 2020, 2021 and 2022. In the article, the green mass yield of maize varieties is close to each other depending on the years of the experiment, and the three-year average green mass yield was analyzed. The obtained data are presented in Figures 1 and 2.

According to the data obtained in the experiment, irrigation was carried out in the order of 60-60-60% of soil moisture before irrigation compared to the limited field moisture capacity, and 74.3 c/ha of green mass was obtained in Uzbekistan-601 ESV maize variety planted as the main crop (on average in 2020-2022). The Karasuv-350 AMV variety irrigated with the same irrigation method produced 76,3 c/ha, and the Uzbekistan-300 MV variety produced 84,4 centners of green mass per hectare in an average of three years.

It should be noted that in the experiment, the soil moisture before irrigation was 60-60-60% in relation to limited field moisture capacity, according to the irrigation order 0-1-0, irrigation was carried out once, the irrigation rate was 1301; 1280; 1310 m³/ha, 70-70-60% irrigation in 1-2-0 system, one-time irrigation rate was 972-1047 m³/ha, and seasonal irrigation rate was 3050; 2974; 2978 m³/ha. It was irrigated in the 1-4-0 system in the order of soil moisture 80-80-60% compared to limited field moisture capacity, with a one-time irrigation rate of 630-740 m³/ha and a seasonal irrigation rate of 3431; 3287; 3407 m³/ha.

The yield of green mass is 91,7 c/ha in the Uzbekistan-601 ESV variety when irrigation is carried out in the order of 70-70-60% of soil moisture in relation to limited field moisture capacity, from Karasuv-350 AMV variety, 87,4 centner

per hectare were obtained, Uzbekistan-300 MV variety was 93,9 c/ha on average in three years. It can be said that in the experiment with 70-70-60% irrigation, high green mass was obtained from maize varieties, 17,4; 11,1; 9,5 c/ha higher green mass yield was achieved for varieties compared to irrigated variants with 60-60-60% soil moisture compared to limited field moisture capacity.

Figure 1. Effect of irrigation regime on green mass yield of maize varieties planted as main crop in c/ha.

Among Uzbekistan-601 ESV, Karasuv-350 AMV and Uzbekistan-300 MV varieties irrigated in the order of irrigation 80-80-60% with pre-irrigation soil moisture relative to limited field moisture capacity, on average, 86,5; 93,3 and 95,3 c/ha of green mass was obtained in three years, respectively and it was noted that the highest green mass was obtained in relation to lower irrigation methods.

Uzbekistan-601 ESV, Karasuv-350 AMV and Uzbekistan-300 MV varieties planted as a repeated crop made it possible to obtain the following green mass when the irrigation method of maize varieties was studied. Irrigation was not required in the regime of 60-60-60% of soil moisture in relation to limited field moisture capacity, and the average amount of green mass was 29,9; 30,9; 32,3 c/ha

in three years.

When irrigating Uzbekistan-601 ESV, Karasuv-350 AMV and Uzbekistan-300 MV maize varieties with 70-70-60% soil moisture in relation to limited field moisture capacity, the average yield for the respective varieties in three years was 33,2, 34,5 and 36,6 c/ha of green mass was obtained and 3,3-3,7 c/ha of additional green mass was provided compared to irrigation in the regime of 60-60-60% of soil moisture in relation to limited field moisture capacity.

In saline, semi-hydromorphic soils, when the pre-irrigation soil moisture is 80-80-60% compared to limited field moisture capacity, the Uzbekistan-601 ESV maize variety has an average yield of 33,4 c/ha in three years, the Karasuv-350 AMV variety has 34,4 centners per hectare, and Uzbekistan-300 MV variety accumulated 35,7 c/ha of green mass.

Figure 4.8.4. Effect of maize varieties planted as a repeated crop on green mass yield c/ha depending on the irrigation regime.

The indicators of the green mass yield of maize varieties were observed in the order of irrigation of 80-80-60% soil moisture before irrigation compared to

limited field moisture capacity. However, since the main goal in the experiment was grain yield, it was observed that the higher irrigation regime resulted in more stem growth and higher green mass of the plants, considering the grain yield in the 70-70-60% irrigation regime.

Conclusion. In general, it can be concluded from the obtained results that in the conditions of moderately saline, meadow-alluvial soils, irrigation of 80-80-60% of pre-irrigation soil moisture compared to limited field moisture capacity of maize varieties contributes to more accumulation of green mass (stems, leaves). However, taking into account soil properties and grain yield, the optimal irrigation method should be 70-70-60%.

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